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RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STUDY INVOLVEMENT AND AFFECT INTENSITY OF B.Ed. COLLEGE TEACHER TRAINEES

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Abstract

The present study aims to explore the relationship between affect intensity and study involvement of B.Ed. college teacher trainees. Since it is a fact finding expedition, survey method was adopted by the investigator. The samples for this investigation were taken from the students studying in six colleges of education (B.Ed. College) in Thanjavour district. Special attention was given to such factors as gender, locality, and educational qualification. 150 B.Ed. college teacher trainees were taken for this investigation as sample by simple random sampling technique. Study Involvement Inventory by Bhatnagar (1982) and Affect Intensity Measure (AIM) by Larsen (1984) were used to collect the data. To analyse the data mean, standard deviation, t' test and correlation analysis were used as statistical techniques. The findings show that (i) there is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. college teacher trainees in their study involvement, (ii) there is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. college teacher trainees in their affect intensity, and (iii) there is a significant relationship between affect intensity and study involvement of B.Ed. college teacher trainees.

Keywords: relationship, affect intensity, study involvement, B.Ed. college teacher trainees

Introduction

Education is a process by which the individual is helped to develop to the full all his innate potentialities, so that he is well equipped for a gracious and harmonious life in the world. Teacher education is defined as "all formal and informal activities and experiences that help to qualify a person to assume the responsibility as a member of the educational profession or to discharge his responsibility most effectively (Good, 1973). Study involvement refers to the process by which it refers to the pursuit of the individual in learning the scholastic pursuit includes abasement, achievement, affiliation, aggression, autonomy, deference, nurturance, order, recognition, succorance when such outside element seem to be pertinent to the action situation. Affect intensity was designed to assess differences in how individuals experience their emotions which affect one's emotionality and emotional expressiveness, such as cultural and socio economic differences.

Significance of the Study

The prime function of education is to develop the personality of the students. Adolescence is the stage of stress and strain, the process of human development that is adolescence has severe emotional problems and they also have identity crises. So the teacher trainees may express severe anxiety and they cannot adjust with the environment. The severe anxiety will affect the academic achievement. The Intensity of the emotion is called affect Intensity. So the adolescents have intensified emotions and they have to cope up with the technological development in the society. So, the investigator wants to find the relationship between affect intensity and study involvement of the B.Ed. college teacher trainees.

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Statement of the Study

Relationship between Study Involvement and Affect Intensity of B.Ed. College Teacher Trainees

Operational Definition of the Key Terms

Relationship means the connection between two variables (Lawrence, 2014). In this study, the connection between study involvement and affect intensity was found out.

Study Involvement as a degree of affect or feeling of being actively involved in one's own learning process (Yan Off, 1973).

Affect Intensity refers to the emotional dispositions and reactions contributing to the prevailing mood of a person.

B.Ed. College Teacher Trainees are the students studying their B.Ed. degree programme after completion of their UG/PG degree in colleges of education (B.Ed. Colleges) affiliated to Tamil Nadu Teachers Education University.

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the level of study involvement of B.Ed. college teacher trainees.
2. To find out the level of affect intensity of B.Ed. college teacher trainees.
3. To find out the relationship between affect intensity and study involvement of B.Ed. college teacher trainees.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. college teacher trainees in their study involvement.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. college teacher trainees in their affect intensity.
3. There is no significant relationship between affect intensity and study involvement of B.Ed. college teacher trainees.

Methods and Procedures

The survey method was followed for this investigation. Since it is a fact finding expedition, this method was adopted by the investigator. The samples for this investigation were taken from the students studying in six colleges of education (B.Ed. College) in Thanjavur district. Special attention was given to such factors as gender, locality, and educational qualification. 150 B.Ed. college teacher trainees were taken for this investigation as sample by simple random sampling technique. Study Involvement Inventory by Bhatnagar (1982) and Affect Intensity Measure (AIM) by Larsen (1984) were used to collect the data. To analyse the data mean, standard deviation, 't' test and correlation analysis were used as statistical techniques.

Analysis and Findings

There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. college teacher trainees in their study involvement.

Table-1

Difference between Male and Female B.Ed. College Teacher Trainees in their Study Involvement

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 0.05 level
Male	75	58.40	6.84	0.253	Not Significant
Female	75	58.66	6.03		

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. college teacher trainees in their study involvement as the calculated value (0.253) is less than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. college teacher trainees in their affect intensity.

Table-2

Difference between Male and Female B.Ed. College Teacher Trainees in their Affect Intensity

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 0.05 level
Male	75	42.97	6.99	1.722	Not Significant
Female	75	45.14	8.39		

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. college teacher trainees in their affect intensity as the calculated value (1.722) is less than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

There is no significant relationship between affect intensity and study involvement of B.Ed. college teacher trainees.

Table-3

Relationship between Affect Intensity and Study Involvement of B.Ed. College Teacher Trainees

Variables	Calculated 'γ' value	Remark at 0.05 level
Study Involvement Vs Affect Intensity	0.281	Significant

It is inferred from the above table that there is significant relationship between affect intensity and study involvement of B.Ed. college teacher trainees as the calculated value (0.281) is greater than the table value (0.256) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion

The present study insists that there is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. college teacher trainees in their study involvement. This finding confirms the findings of Jency & Punitha Mary (2010), Mohamedayupkhan & Mani (2012), Sudhakar & Selvakumar (2013), Maharishi & Parameswari (2013), Reena & Boruwa (2014) and contradicts the finding of Pangat (2014). When comparing the mean scores female teacher trainees are better than male teacher trainees in their study involvement. This may be due to the fact that female teacher trainees are highly motivated and they are having very high goal.

There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. college teacher trainees in their affect intensity. When comparing the mean scores, female teacher trainees are better than male teacher trainees in their affect intensity. This finding confirms the findings of Jency & Punitha Mary (2010). This may be due to the fact that female teacher trainees are good in relieving their stress and are highly motivated.

The correlation analysis shows that there is a significant relationship between study involvement and affect intensity of B.Ed. college teacher trainees. This may be due to the fact that study involvement is based on the emotion of the learners. Thus, the Affect Intensity is balancing the effects of study involvement.

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